

Immobilization of lipase in ordered mesoporous materials: Effect of textural and structural parameters

Elías Serra ^a, Álvaro Mayoral ^{b,c}, Yasuhiro Sakamoto ^b, Rosa M. Blanco ^a, Isabel Díaz ^{a,*}

^a Instituto de Catálisis y Petroleoquímica, CSIC, CI Marie Curie 2, Cantoblanco, 28049-Madrid, Spain

^b Structural Chemistry, Arrhenius Laboratory, Stockholm University, SE-10691 Stockholm, Sweden

^c School of Chemistry, University of Birmingham, Edgbaston, Birmingham B15 2TT, United Kingdom

Abstract

A systematic study dealing with the influence of several parameters on the immobilization of lipase in ordered mesoporous materials (OMM) is presented here. In a first step, a series of OMM have been synthesized trying to cover the most relevant structures. The aim is to get variation in the key properties susceptible of influencing their behavior as lipase supports, such as the structure (cubic or hexagonal), the nature of the pores (channel-like or cage-like), the connectivity of the porous network and the pore size. Also, by following the co-condensation technique, 5–10%-methylated analogues of the pure-silica materials have been prepared. All the samples have been fully characterized with XRD, TEM (including 3D reconstruction), SEM, TGA and N₂ isotherms, and the incorporation of the organic function has been demonstrated by ²⁹Si NMR. All of them have been tested as supports in the immobilization of *Candida antarctica* Lipase B (CaLB) and the leaching of the enzyme in aqueous media evaluated. With such a systematic approach, valuable information on the influence of the textural properties and the nature of the porous network on the yields of immobilization and enzyme desorption have been stated. Very interestingly, leaching of the enzyme can be diminished until it practically disappears without being covalently bonded to the wall, which places the ordered mesoporous materials at the starting point of a new scenario in enzyme immobilization on preexisting supports.

Keywords: Ordered mesoporous materials; Lipase; Enzyme immobilization

1. Introduction

It is known that zeolites are, both academic and industrially, one of the most important families of porous materials. However, the relatively small size of their pores (usually below 1.2 nm) is an important drawback that hinders their application in processes where the diffusion of bulky molecules is required [1]. That is why the discovery of the ordered mesoporous materials (OMM) in 1992 had a major impact on the scientific community [2].

The advantageous features of the OMM over the previously available amorphous mesoporous silicas prepared by

conventional sol–gel methods make them potentially ideal enzyme carriers. Especially, the optimum control of the textural properties allows designing and customizing the mesostructure for specific applications [2–9]. Furthermore, the good connectivity of the porous network and the small particle size offer the possibility of minimizing diffusional hindrance during the catalytic performance that usually results in a loss of activity of the immobilized enzyme. This possibility was explored soon, and since the pioneer works by Díaz and Balkus in 1996 [10] many different enzymes have been encapsulated in the OMM.

In the first attempts, the relatively small pore size of the M41S materials (typically around 5 nm) limited the applicability to small-sized enzymes such as trypsin, papain or cytochrome *c*. However, the arrival of the SBA family of

OMM, discovered in the University of Santa Barbara in 1998 [3], reopened and expanded the field to medium or even large proteins. In contrast with those of the M41S type, these materials are synthesized in strongly acidic media by using nonionic copolymers as surfactants, and specially triblock copolymers. These amphiphilic molecules, commercially known as Pluronics, are formed by a central fragment of polypropylene oxide (PPO) that acts as hydrophobic tail, and two lateral chains of polyethylene oxide (PEO) as polar heads. As a result, the OMM with larger pore sizes and thicker walls, thus enhanced hydrothermal stability and better perspectives of application, are obtained. The most representative example is the SBA-15 [4], an analogue of MCM-41 synthesized with P123, a Pluronic with formula $(\text{PEO})_{20}(\text{PPO})_{70}(\text{PEO})_{20}$. Its average pore diameter is usually around 8 nm, although it can be theoretically expanded up to 30 nm, which makes it a better candidate for the immobilization of enzymes.

Another interesting possibility offered by the OMM is to encapsulate macromolecules in large cages that are connected by smaller windows and arranged into different cubic structures. A representative example is the SBA-16, synthesized with the Pluronic F127 $((\text{PEO})_{106}(\text{PPO})_{70}(\text{PEO})_{106})$ in which the cages are disposed in body centered cubic structure following the *Im-3m* symmetry [3].

However, the originally reported SBA-16 suffered of relatively small cage size (up to only 5.4 nm), what together with a considerably smaller size of the interconnecting entrances hindered its application as a suitable enzymatic support. With the passage of time, Ryoo and collaborators were able to combine the preexisting techniques to expand and control the cage and the window size [5–8]. By increasing the temperature and duration of the hydrothermal treatment and by adding increasing proportions of P123 to the F127 surfactant, they demonstrated how both parameters could be independently tailored [8]. Another important achievement in the quest of useful OMM for the entrapment of enzymes is the FDU-12, developed in the Fudan University by Zhao and collaborators [7]. With the base of the SBA-16 they obtained a cage-like face-centered cubic material, a more compacted and better connected mesoporous network. These properties, together with cage and entrance diameters larger than those of SBA-16, made this material a promising candidate for the immobilization of enzymes. Actually, it was tested as a lysozyme carrier in the same paper where its synthesis was described, showing a better performance than SBA-16 [7].

Another important family of material is the KIT, developed in the Korean Advanced Institute of Science and Technology. The innovative point of these OMM is that, through the use of low concentrations of acid, the kinetics of the mesophase formation is slowed down, giving rise to an almost thermodynamic control of the process and making the structure more susceptible to changes. The material KIT-6 is of special interest. A cubic bicontinuous *Ia-3d* structure is obtained by using P123 as template and

through the addition of KCl and butanol [9]. Unlike MCM-48, its analogue synthesized with cationic surfactants, the pore size of this OMM (typically around 8 nm) is large enough to accommodate medium-sized proteins and can be synthesized in a broad range of conditions without structural defects. Moreover, its advantageous features in terms of connectivity, with a very open network and two simultaneous systems of channels, make it an ideal candidate for the adsorption of enzymes.

All these advances, together with the possibility of functionalizing the silica walls with a broad range of organic groups, make the OMM potential candidates to improve the performance of traditional amorphous mesoporous silica. Since the first study by Balkus and Díaz in 1996 [10], a lot of enzymes have been encapsulated ([11,12]). In the particular case of lipases, although some promising results have been achieved, there is still room for improvement. Above all, there is a lack of systematic studies clearly stating the influence of some crucial factors (such as the pore shape and size or the internal structure) on the immobilization process, as well as on the subsequent application of the supports as heterogeneous biocatalysts. Lipase dimensions (usually around 4 nm) fit well with common OMM, but the confinement is still strong and makes the application of strong links (such as covalent) difficult. As Wright stated in a recent review, pores at least three times larger than the enzyme are required to make covalent bonding barely possible [11] (this does not mean that internal diffusion hindrance disappear). In the present day these pore diameters, although possible, are still unusual, and the attempts to immobilize lipase covalently on OMM have resulted in low activities [13].

Discarded for the moment the covalent bonding, the adsorption by weaker forces (such as van der Waals or electrostatic interactions) has also been tested, showing the expected stabilizing effect characteristic of the confinement in nanospaces [14]. However, leaching of the enzyme is now a main issue [15]. Some attempts to avoid it such as the silylation of the external pore openings have proven to be not efficient, as the protein gets partially denatured. ([16,17]).

The best results in this field have arrived by the use of hydrophobic interactions. Lipases are known from many years ago to have a very hydrophobic domain on its external surface that makes them capable of interacting with hydrophobic substrates or interphases [18]. This feature has been very largely used to promote its immobilization on insoluble supports ([19,20]) and has also yielded the best results with OMM so far. For example, FDU-12 functionalized with octyl groups, together with the application of high pressures, led to high lipase loadings and reduced the leaching to a minimum, achieving an efficient confinement of the enzyme inside the cages [21]. However, this strategy is difficult to generalize, as it requires the packing of the OMM in a chromatographic column. Anchoring of butyl groups was less effective, and resulted in even lower lipase loading than the siliceous counterparts, although it

was probably due to the additional reduction of size in a material that already had too small pores (less than 4 nm) [22].

What we propose here is a systematic study in which the role of some key parameters on the immobilization of lipase in OMM can be clarified. With that aim, a set of OMM with different structures and pore sizes has been synthesized, trying to cover the most relevant materials and structures. Also, methylated analogues of the materials have been prepared by the co-condensation method (one-pot synthesis) to study the effect of a slight degree of hydrophobization. The specific enzyme used here is lipase from *Candida antarctica* B (CaLB), used in crude extract as received from Novozymes. Its molecular weight is 32 kDa, its dimensions $3 \times 4 \times 5$ nm [23], and its immobilization on siliceous materials by hydrophobic interactions is well documented [24,25].

2. Experimental

2.1. Synthesis of pure silica and methylated OMM

In order to obtain a set of materials with different and well-defined structures, synthesis procedures described in the literature have been followed. A careful selection of the literature based on the premises stated in the introduction has led us to the selection of reliable, unambiguously resolved samples, covering the main kind of structures that have been obtained in both channel-like and cage-like systems, and displaying large pores and/or cages/windows: *p6mm* (SBA-15) [4], *Ia-3d* (KIT-6) [9], *Im-3m* (SBA-16) [8] and *Fm-3m* (FDU-12) [7]. All samples were prepared in acid media with triblock copolymeric (Pluronic) surfactants and tetraethoxysilane (TEOS) as silica source. Details for the synthesis of each material are available on the corresponding references. In all the cases, we have moved to the compositions and conditions yielding the largest pores.

Additionally, methylated materials were synthesized via co-condensation of TEOS and methyltriethoxysilane (MTEOS). The molar composition was 95% TEOS–5% MTEOS in all the cases, except for the methylated FDU-12 samples that was made out of 90% TEOS–10% MTEOS. These samples will be denoted thereby by adding the prefix Me to the name of the material, that is, Me-SBA-15, Me-KIT-6, Me-SBA-16 and Me-FDU-12.

Removal of the surfactant was made by calcination at 550 °C under consecutive N₂/air streams in the pure-silica samples and by extraction with ethanol in the methylated ones. Complete surfactant removal was checked by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA).

2.2. Characterization of the OMM

All the samples were extensively characterized with a combination of several techniques. XRD was performed in a Seifert XRD 3000P diffractometer operating at low angle. For the transmission electron microscopy observa-

tions, the materials were crushed, dispersed in acetone or ethanol and dropped on a holey carbon grid. Selected area electron diffraction (SAED) patterns and TEM images were obtained in a JEOL JEM2000FX operating at 200 kV, and a JEOL JEM3010 operating at 300 kV in low dose conditions. For the three-dimensional (3D) reconstructions, the crystal structure factors of the crystal, which include both the phase and the amplitude, were extracted from several primary TEM images. The three-dimensional pore structures can be obtained by inverse Fourier transformation of the crystal structure factors with the combination of total pore volume, which can be obtained from N₂ isotherm, and silica wall density. SEM micrographs were collected with a JEOL JSM 6400 Philips XL30 operating at 20 kV. Nitrogen adsorption/desorption isotherms were carried out at –196 °C in a Micromeritics TriStar3000 apparatus. Specific surface areas were deduced by using the BET method and the pore size distribution by applying the BJH protocol to the adsorption branch of the isotherm. TGA thermograms were recorded on a Perkin–Elmer TGA7 equipment, scanning a temperature range of 20–900 °C at a heating rate of 20 °C/min. Finally, ²⁹Si NMR of the methylated samples was performed on a Bruker AV400 spectrometer, using $\pi/3$ of 4 μ s pulses at 240 s intervals. Samples were spined at the magic angle at 5 kHz, and the quantification was carried out adjusting to Gaussian curves.

2.3. Lipase immobilization

The commercial extract CaLB supplied by Novozymes had a protein concentration of 8 mg/ml, determined by the Bradford assay [26]. Different amounts of this extract (in the range 0.25–2.5 ml) were dissolved in 50 mM phosphate buffer at pH 5, up to a total volume of 20 ml. To that solution, 100 mg of the OMM were added and left in suspension with a helicoidal stirrer. Aliquots were taken at given times, and the enzymatic activity of suspension and supernatant towards the hydrolysis of *p*-nitrophenylacetate (*p*-NPA) was determined. The activity of supernatant decreases as the enzyme molecules get anchored to the support. When the decrease in the activity reaches a minimum and constant value, it means that no more enzyme can be immobilized. The time needed for this constant or null value is what we call contact time. The suspension was then filtered off and washed twice with acetone. Finally, the solid was dried at room temperature, collected and weighted. The activity of the suspension, including both the supernatant and the solid, was also monitored to check whether it is kept constant throughout the immobilization process.

Apart from those OMM whose synthesis is described in Sections 2.1 and 2.2, another two materials have been tested: (a) MCM-41 with a pore diameter of 4.7 nm (characterized in Ref. [27]) and (b) amorphous mesoporous silica, denoted as SA, with large pores (27.9 nm) and disordered structure. This sample was a kind donation of Silica PQ Corporation, (Valley Forge, PA, USA). For detailed characterization, see Ref. [24].

2.4. Enzyme leaching

To measure the leaching of lipase from the supports, a sample of the solid containing the enzyme was suspended in 50 mM phosphate buffer at pH 7. The solid/liquid ratio was 1.25 mg/ml, which implies a four times more diluted medium than during the immobilization. At different times aliquots of the suspensions were withdrawn and centrifuged, and the protein content of the supernatants was determined according to Bradford assay [26].

2.5. *p*-NPA hydrolysis activity assay

This method was used as a routine assay to monitor the incorporation of lipase inside the OMM. The reaction was followed in a Kontron spectrophotometer equipped with stirring device and temperature controller. 1.9 ml of the substrate solution (0.4 mM *p*-NPA dissolved in 50 mM phosphate buffer at pH 7) was poured into the cubette. Once diluted to give a measurable value, 50 μ l of supernatant or suspension aliquots were added. Finally, the increase of absorbance at a wavelength of 348 nm and 25 $^{\circ}$ C due to the release of *p*-nitrophenol was measured ($\epsilon = 5150 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$).

2.6. Tributyrin hydrolysis activity assay

This reaction was used to check the hydrolytic activity of the supported biocatalysts. The reaction rate was followed by the titration of the released butyric acid in a Mettler Toledo DL-50 pH-state with 0.1 N NaOH. 1.47 ml of glycidyl tributyrinate (tributyrin) were added under stirring to 48.5 ml of 10 mM phosphate buffer at pH 7 in a thermostated glass. Once equilibrated at pH 7, 5 mg of the biocatalyst were added, and the rate of consumption of NaOH to maintain the pH at 7 was measured. One unit of activity corresponds to 1 μ mol of tributyrin converted per minute.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of pure silica and methylated OMM

As stated before, four different kinds of materials have been synthesized (Fig. 1), two of them exhibiting channel-

like (SBA-15 and KIT-6) and two with cage-like pores (SBA-16 and FDU-12).

For clarifying purposes, the section is divided into two sub-sections: one for the channel-like and another one for the cage-like materials.

3.1.1. Channel-like OMM

Both materials have been prepared in two compositions: pure silica and 5%-methylated. X-ray diffractograms of the four samples (see Supplementary information) are in good accordance with those expected from the literature, showing the main characteristic peaks characteristics of the hexagonal *p6mm* plane group (SBA-15 and Me-SBA-15) and of the cubic *Ia-3d* space group (KIT-6 and Me-KIT-6).

To corroborate the high degree of structural order, TEM analysis of the samples was carried out. The corresponding plane and space groups were assigned, thanks to the application of tilting series to obtain electron diffraction patterns along the different axes.

It is known that the shape of the beads can play an important role in their behavior as enzyme carriers [28]. The analysis of the samples by SEM revealed, for both siliceous and methylated SBA-15, the typical SBA-15 morphology, consisting of small rod-like particles of around 1 μ m, that are further aggregated into approximately 70 μ m long wheat-like structures [4]. The KIT-6 samples also maintain the described morphology, in which the polyhedral particles typical of MCM-48 materials (prepared with cationic surfactants) lost their individual nature, aggregating into larger entities [9]. Some representative examples of TEM and SEM micrographs are shown in Fig. 2.

Once the structure has been corroborated, a precise knowledge of the textural properties is required. Factors such as the surface area or the average pore diameter are known to have crucial influence on both immobilization process and catalytic performance of the supported biocatalyst. N_2 adsorption/desorption isotherms of all the four materials are of type IV, with the steep increase typical of mesoporous solids at a relative pressure of around 0.75 (see Fig. 3). The presence of a hysteresis cycle defined by the IUPAC as H1 is closely associated with channel-like large pores.

Surface area and pore volume have been deduced from the BET model (see Table 1). The high values confirm

Fig. 1. Structure of the four OMM synthesized. Starting from the left, SBA-15 (*p6mm*), KIT-6 (*Ia-3d*), SBA-16 (*Im-3m*) and FDU-12 (*Fm-3m*).

Fig. 2. SEM (a and c) and TEM (b and d) micrographs of samples Me-SBA-15 (a and b) and Me-KIT-6 (c and d).

the high porosity of the networks, and also a good wall/solid ratio. In order to obtain the pore size distribution and average diameters, BJH model has been applied to the adsorption branch. This method is known to underestimate the diameter of the mesopores, but is still the most widely used nowadays. Although the results arising from its application cannot be considered as “real” values, they can be used for comparative purposes with confidence. More recent developments that correct the deviation introduced by the Kelvin equation (that neglects adsorbate-adsorbent interactions) are based on the non-local density functional theory (NLDFT) [29,30], but the software application is not widespread yet.

As expected, the organic function has caused a small decrease in the pore size (0.9 and 0.7 nm for SBA-15 and KIT-6, respectively). However, even neglecting the BJH inherent underestimation, all the materials exhibit pores larger than 7.7 nm, far over the biggest CaLB dimension (5 nm).

Fig. 3. N₂ adsorption isotherms of SBA-15 (a), Me-SBA-15 (b), Me-KIT-6 (c) and Me-KIT-6 (d).

Table 1
Textural properties and immobilization results of channel-like samples

Material	D_p (nm)	S_{BET} (m ² /g)	V_p (cm ³ /g)	t_c^a (min)	Loading ^b (mg/g)
MCM-41	4.7	595	0.82	1440	10
SA	27.9	305	2.70	120	45
SBA-15	8.8	890	1.31	120	44
Me-SBA-15	7.9	794	1.01	200	23
KIT-6	8.4	917	1.20	280	37
Me-KIT-6	7.7	984	1.29	50	35

^a Time at which the maximum loading is achieved.

^b Maximum enzymatic loading, expressed in milligrams of enzyme per gram of solid.

Finally, the incorporation of the methyl moieties attached to the inner walls has been confirmed by ²⁹Si NMR. Fig. 4 shows the spectra of the methylated samples Me-SBA-15 and Me-KIT-6, where four resonances can be seen at chemical shifts of -110, -100 and -90, corresponding to Q⁴ ((SiO)₄Si), Q³ ((SiO)₃SiOH) and Q² ((SiO)₂Si(OH)₂) silicon species, respectively, with decreasing degree of condensation. The signals at -64 can be attributed to T³ silicon atoms bonded to a methyl group and three siloxanes ((SiO)₃Si(CH₃)) [31].

Although Q⁴ was the majority signal, a high relative abundance of Q³ species reveals a moderate degree of condensation, probably due to the method used to remove the surfactant (extraction instead of calcination). Anyway, a big number of condensation defects are typically observed in the OMM. The inclusion of the methyl group is evidenced by the T³ peak. Quantification can be carried out by deconvolution of the curves into gaussian lines. The results (overwritten on the figure) show a complete incorporation of the organic moiety into the inorganic skeleton, even exceeding the 5% molar percentage present in the initial gel.

3.1.2. Cage-like OMM

As in the samples above, Me-SBA-16 has been prepared from a gel containing a 5% of methyl groups, while in the

Fig. 4. ^{29}Si NMR spectra of Me-SBA-15 (left) and Me-KIT-6 (right).

case of the FDU-12 this value is 10%. The interpretation of the diffractograms is not straightforward (see [Supplementary Information](#)). Although SBA-16 materials (and especially Me-SBA-16) can be roughly indexed to the $Im-3m$ space group, in all the cases main reflections appear at very low angles, at which the reliability of the results would be controversial with this equipment.

TEM analysis is therefore required. Electron diffraction studies coupled with images reveal a highly ordered $Im-3m$ structure for both SBA-16 and Me-SBA-16. FDU-12 also corresponds with the expected space group, although it exhibits a lot of stacking defects. However, its counterpart Me-FDU-12, that differs from the other methylated samples in a higher percentage of organic groups, presents a disordered foam-like structure, with some short-range structured domains but without long-range ordering.

The analysis by SEM reveals the globular morphology characteristic of these kind of solids, with different polyhedral particles depending on the space group. These particles, that are 1–10 μm large, are further aggregated in different degrees. Examples of SEM and TEM micrographs for methylated samples are shown in [Fig. 5](#).

N_2 adsorption isotherms are plotted in [Fig. 6](#). The four cage-like materials present type IV isotherms, with an H2 hysteresis cycle that is usually associated with cage-like pores. Values for the surface area can be calculated using the BET model as with channel-like OMM. However, the deduction of the pore diameters is more complex this time. To obtain the size of the main cages the BJH model has been applied to the adsorption branch again, although this methodology is even more defective than for the channel-like mesoporous materials, with up to 100% errors [32]. Traditionally, BJH method has also been applied to the desorption branch of the isotherm to get the size of the interconnecting windows. However, in the last years it has been demonstrated that, due to the instability of the meniscus, N_2 always evacuates at a similar relative pressure of around 0.45 independently of the size of the windows [33], which very often leads to diameters of around

Fig. 5. SEM (a and c) and TEM (b and d) micrographs of samples Me-SBA-16 (a and b) and Me-FDU-12 (c and d).

3.5 nm. In the last few years, this approach has been considered wrong, and different groups are trying to develop protocols to deduce the entrance diameter from the N_2 adsorption isotherms [6,32] although there is no absolutely reliable method yet.

On the other hand, a precise knowledge of both dimensions would be required for a rigorous study of their influence on the immobilization performance. With that aim, electron crystallography [33] has been applied to reconstruct 3D structure of SBA-16 ($a = 15.2$ nm) and Me-SBA-16 ($a = 16.5$ nm) materials. Their crystal structure factors, both phase and amplitudes, have been extracted from the TEM micrographs taken along [100] [110] and [111] directions (see [Supplementary information](#)). 3D reconstructed pore structures were obtained by making inverse Fourier transform of their crystal structure factors as shown in [Fig. 7](#). The total pore volume measured from

Fig. 6. N₂ adsorption isotherms of SBA-16 (a), Me-SBA-16 (b), FDU-12 (c) and Me-FDU-12 (d).

Fig. 7. 3D reconstructed pore structure and crystal structure factors of samples SBA-16 (a) and Me-SBA-16 (b).

N₂ adsorption and silica wall density were used to decide the threshold value of the boundary of silica wall and mesopore from electrostatic potential distribution.

As it can be seen in Table 2, all the cavity sizes are large (over 8.8 nm). In the samples in which the 3D reconstruction is available (SBA-16 and Me-SBA-16), a considerable discrepancy between the values obtained by both methods is observed. The reconstruction yields not only 50% higher

sizes (thus confirming the underestimation introduced by the BJH method) but also the order is inverted, finally resulting the Me-SBA-16 sample larger than the pure-silica one, in both cavity and window size. Thanks to this technique, we can also check that the method applied to enlarge the windows via prolonged hydrothermal treatments has been successful, resulting in up to 6 nm entrances in Me-SBA-16.

Table 2
Textural properties and immobilization results of cage-like samples

Material	D_p^a (nm)	D_p^b (nm)	S_{BET} (m ² /g)	V_p (cm ³ /g)	t_c^c (min)	Loading ^d (mg/g)
SA	27.9	–	305	2.70	120	45
SBA-16	10.2	12.3 (4.6)	659	0.73	1440	5
Me-SBA-16	8.8	13.1 (5.9)	508	0.85	1440	30
FDU-12	10.4	–	261	0.38	1440	28
Me-FDU-12	9.7	–	628	0.98	10	37

^a Determined by applying the BJH method to the adsorption branch of the isotherms.

^b Extracted from the 3D reconstruction. Window sizes in brackets.

^c Time at which the maximum loading is achieved.

^d Maximum enzymatic loading, expressed in milligrams of enzyme per gram of solid.

Fig. 8. ^{29}Si NMR spectra of Me-SBA-16 (left) and Me-FDU-12 (right).

^{29}Si NMR spectra of both the methylated materials are shown in Fig. 8. Results are similar to those obtained for the channel-like OMM, with a big prominence of Q^4 silicon atoms accompanied by less abundant Q^3 and Q^2 , indicative of an incomplete condensation. The correct anchoring of the methyl groups is evidenced by the T^3 peak appearing at -64 ppm. However, the incorporation of the organic moieties is not complete in this case: 4% in the Me-SBA-16, prepared from a gel with an initial methyl concentration of 5%; and 7% in the Me-FDU-12, with an initial gel 10% methylated.

3.2. Lipase immobilization, leaching and enzymatic activity of the supports

Once the structure and the incorporation of the methyl groups in the functionalized samples have been corroborated, all the synthesized OMM, along with the two additional materials mentioned in Section 2.3, have been used in the immobilization of CaLB.

Some preliminary experiments showed that the optimum pH for the encapsulation was 5. Under those conditions the silica walls, with an isoelectric point (pI) around 2 [34], are negatively charged, while the enzyme, with a pI of 6 [23], is positively charged. Therefore, the support-enzyme interaction can be visualized as an unspecific electrostatic attraction. This mechanism has already been described and successfully used for other enzymes such as cytochrome *c*, papain, trypsin [10] or chloroperoxidase [35]. Also in the case of our methylated samples, the possible hydrophobic affinity is expected to contribute.

As all the lipases, CaLB possesses a highly hydrophobic domain on its external surface that makes it capable to interact with hydrophobic interphases. In the case of very hydrophobic residues such as long aliphatic chains, intense links can be formed. However, when the hydrophobicity of the functional group is limited, as in the case of the methyl

groups, only a certain degree of affinity of the enzyme towards the covered walls is expected.

Taking into account all these preliminary considerations, the influence of several factors over the immobilization of the lipase on the OMM, on its leaching from the inner structure in aqueous media and on the biocatalyst activity is carefully studied and analyzed. These factors are the effects of the pore size (and the window size in the cases in which we confidently know them), their shape (cage-like or channel-like), the degree of connectivity and tortuosity of the networks and the presence of the methyl moieties. The results have again been divided into two sub-sections, one for channel-like and another one for cage-like OMM that will finally be compared with each other.

3.2.1. Lipase immobilization in channel-like OMM

In Table 1, the main results arising from the immobilization of CaLB in this type of materials are summarized, together with the main textural properties of the OMM: pore diameter (D_p), specific surface area (S_{BET}) and pore volume (V_p). These parameters will be crucial for the subsequent discussion. The contact time (t_c) is the time required to reach a constant activity of the supernatant towards the hydrolysis of p-NPA, indicative of maximum loading in the solid. Contact time is different for all the materials tested and cannot be standardized since each of them requires different time to achieve maximum enzyme loading. The enzyme loading is expressed in milligrams of enzyme per gram of silica.

Data for amorphous silica SA (45 mg/g) are included for comparison purposes, stating the importance of the pore diameter, something that had already been highlighted in the first studies of this type [10], and that has also been observed in other mesoporous solids such as controlled-pore glasses [36]. According to these results, obtained by Bosley and Clayton, restrictions to the access of enzyme into the channels should only disappear when the pores

are 4- to 5-fold than the enzyme diameter. Since the largest dimension of our lipase is 5 nm, the material SA represents immobilization in the absence of size restrictions, while in all the OMM this factor should somehow limit the efficiency. As the pore diameter increases, the diffusion of lipase through the inner channels gets easier, what accelerates the process and should finally result in shorter contact times (t_c). At the same time, a larger pore is more difficult to block, enabling more enzyme to penetrate into the core so that the final loading increases.

Fig. 9 shows how that tendency is manifested in our case by just representing the data from Table 1 for the all-silica samples, plotting the enzymatic loading and the t_c against the average pore diameter, and neglecting the influence of the different structures. Increasing enzyme content accompanied by decreasing contact times is observed when we follow the series moving to larger pores: MCM-41 (4.7 nm), KIT-6 (8.4 nm) and SBA-15 (8.8 nm). However, there is no significant difference between this last sample and the amorphous silica SA (27.9), despite owing almost three times larger pores. It is also worth mentioning that the different structures, and consequently different degrees of connectivity and tortuosity of the different materials, do not seem to have a major influence on their behavior as carriers, which is an unexpected result. Only the pore size seems to matter, while the better connectivity and bigger tortuosity offered by the tri-dimensional cubic network of the KIT-6 do not result in any improvement with respect to the uni-dimensional pores of the SBA-15 (the micropores connecting the main mesopores in this sample are useless for the enzyme diffusion).

Therefore, for silica OMM with channel-like pores, the influence of the pore diameter disappears at a value of around 9 nm, e.g. around twice the largest enzyme dimension. This is significantly different than the conclusion extracted by Bosley and Clayton, as the critical diameter is this time much smaller. The factor causing such a big difference is probably the particle size. The particles of the controlled-pore glasses were between 50 and 500 μm [36],

Fig. 9. Variation of t_c and enzymatic loading as a function of the diameter of the pores.

whereas the SEM micrographs for our OMM revealed particle sizes between 1 and 10 μm . Such a small particles almost eliminate the diffusional impedances, that only become apparent when the pores are so small that the enzyme almost does not fit (less than twice its size).

Other textural properties, such as pore volume or surface area, do not have influence as they are not limiting in this case. Simple calculations based on the volume and surface occupied by the enzyme can corroborate that these values are negligible compared with the total ones.

Both methylated materials (Me-SBA-15 and Me-KIT-6) present smaller loadings than their siliceous analogues. The presence of the methyl moieties did not provide enough hydrophobicity to improve the efficiency of the process by increasing the affinity of the lipase for the inner walls. More hydrophobic groups are probably required, as has been evidenced in experiments performed with octyl and butyl groups [21,22]. However, these longer chains would very likely reduce significantly the size of the pores, thus having a negative effect.

3.2.1.1. *Leaching of enzyme from channel-like OMM.* The non-covalent nature of enzyme-support linkage through only electrostatic interactions is not enough to retain the protein within the siliceous materials. Therefore, under different pH or dilution conditions, a leakage is expected towards outside the particles unless the structural features of pores may avoid it, at least in the non-methylated samples. Leaching experiments were also performed with lipase immobilized on SA amorphous silica for comparative purposes. The derivatives were resuspended at a pH over the isoelectric point to generate charge repulsions and facilitate the leaching of the enzyme. In the case of methylated materials, the possible effect of additional hydrophobic interactions can also be detected.

Fig. 10 summarizes these results, plotting the percentage of leached enzyme with time for all the materials. Two dif-

Fig. 10. Leaching of enzyme from channel-like materials. Expressed as percent of the initial enzyme leached on each material as a function of time.

ferent kinds of patterns can be distinguished. On one hand, SA and SBA-15 suffer a continuous leaching, without reaching an equilibrium point in the range of time studied (up to 2 h). In the previous section, it was stated that diffusional problems were negligible in both of them, which led to a maximum and very similar enzyme content despite the huge difference in pore size. Now, when the supported samples are suspended in aqueous solution, the resistance to the exit of enzyme is also small, and pore blocking is unlikely. However, their behaviors were not exactly the same as during the immobilization, but the leaching is more marked in the SA, which is manifested in steeper slope. Therefore, and despite the fact that the pore size of SBA-15 is big enough to neglect diffusional problems during the entrance of lipase, it does offer some resistance to its exit. This advantage of SBA-15 over SA is an example of the benefits offered by the confinement in nanospaces, characteristic of the encapsulation of biological entities in OMM.

On the other hand, the rest of materials (Me-SBA-15, KIT-6 and Me-KIT-6) exhibit a marked saturation profile, reaching a maximum at short times (around 20–30 min) that is not exceeded when they are left longer under suspension. This shows that although the better connectivity did not result in any improvement on enzyme content or contact time, the tortuosity inherent to three-dimensional network of both methylated and pure-silica KIT-6 samples hinders the diffusion of lipase, thus reducing its leaching. Above all, the abundance of interconnecting elbows facilitates the blockage of the porous network. This effect is the opposite than that observed in drug delivery systems, in which the use of three-dimensional networks is known to ease the leaching of the guest molecule [37,38].

In the case of the Me-SBA-15, the difference with respect to its siliceous counterpart can only be explained by the presence of the methyl groups. Although they are not hydrophobic enough to improve the immobilization, they can force the anchoring of entrapped CaLB molecules in certain areas with high density of functional groups, which together with the bad connectivity of the plane group *p6mm* limits the leaching.

In general terms, it seems that some factors that did not affect the immobilization, as the tortuosity, the presence of methyl groups or the pore size above 9 nm, do play a role in the leaching in aqueous media. When the lipase is occluded in the porous network, it can probably orientate in an advantageous way, allowing a better interaction with the silica wall that makes the process more sensitive to all these factors, thus providing certain irreversibility.

3.2.1.2. Hydrolytic activity of the channel-like supports.

Finally, the activity of the derivatives was tested in the reaction of tributyrin hydrolysis. The aim is to check if the enzyme preserves its activity when it is confined in very restricted spaces, barely larger than its own dimensions. Results are summarized in Fig. 11. The specific activity is expressed in tributyrin units (μ moles of TB converted in a minute) per mg of lipase. Data for the siliceous and meth-

Fig. 11. Activity of channel-like derivatives. Expressed in units of tributyrin converted per milligram of enzyme inside the solid.

ylated samples are shown for each OMM (SBA-15 and KIT-6).

Diffusional restrictions of substrate may be influenced by particle size and pore diameter. Former experiments performed in our laboratory (unpublished results) with CaLB immobilized on the amorphous silica aforementioned showed how diffusional restrictions for tributyrin hydrolysis disappeared when particle size was reduced below 1 μ m. Our OMM are in the μ m range, therefore, substrate diffusional restrictions due to particle size have been neglected in this discussion. Pore diameter may also affect, and actually this source of diffusional restrictions should be operating in all our systems. However, all pore sizes are in a narrow range (8–9 nm) so probably the contribution of this phenomenon is similar in all of them and therefore all the reaction rates may still be compared.

The data on Fig. 11 show that derivatives obtained from methylated OMM display higher activity than those from unfunctionalized samples. This is probably the result of two parallel effects. On one side, the slightly hydrophobic nature of the methylated porous walls enables the enzyme to orientate with its hydrophobic domain facing to the walls. This prevents the aggregation of enzymes through their respective hydrophobic lids, a very common phenomenon in concentrated solutions that leads to decreased activity. On the other hand, the main substrate of the reaction (tributyrin) is a very hydrophobic molecule with very low solubility in water, and its entrance and diffusion through the network are favored when the walls are hydrophobized. This improvement was somehow expected, as the increase of catalytic activity towards hydrophobic substrates due to methyl functionalization had already been observed in ordered mesoporous materials [39]. Moreover, one of the products of the reaction (glycerol) is highly hydrophilic, so its exit from the hydrophobic environment into the bulk solution is also favored. The result of all this is an increase in the global reaction rate.

3.2.2. Lipase immobilization in cage-like OMM

In the same way as for the channel-like materials, the results are summarized in Table 2. Data for SA are also included for comparison.

It is easy to see the qualitative gap in the values of contact time. While the channel-like materials achieved the maximum loading in around 2 h, 24 h is now required to reach the equilibrium in most of the cases. This is an effect of the small-sized windows (close to the size of lipase) giving access to the cages. Actually and although we only have reliable data for the window sizes in two of the samples (SBA-16 and Me-SBA-16), it is very likely that the entrances are smaller than one or several dimensions of the lipase ($3 \times 4 \times 5$ nm) as windows larger than 5 nm are uncommon. Due to this restriction, the enzyme must orientate in the proper direction to be able to diffuse along the network from one cage to another, which dramatically slows down the process.

The only siliceous sample for which the size of the windows is known is SBA-16. The size of its window is very similar to the pore diameter of the MCM-41 (4.6 and 4.7 nm, respectively, see Tables 1 and 2). In fact, both samples require the same time to reach the equilibrium (24 h). However, the corresponding loading achieved, although very low in both cases, is higher in the channel-like MCM-41 (10 against 5 mg/g). In this case, in which space is so restricted and a particular orientation of the enzyme is required, the higher tortuosity inherent to the body-centered cubic structure of the SBA-16 against the unidirectional system of channels of the SBA-15 is crucial, giving rise to a less efficient immobilization. This did not happen in the other channel-like samples, in which the dimensions were roomier and consequently the diffusion quicker. The other siliceous sample with cage-like pores (FDU-12) required longer contact times, although it resulted in much higher loadings (28 mg/g). Despite the lack of accurate information about window diameter in FDU-12, immobilization data seems to corroborate that FDU-12 has larger windows than SBA-16. Actually, this would be an indirect method to evaluate the openings between the cages if the linearity of the phenomenon was confirmed, as with the pore diameter below 9 nm in channel-like materials.

Regarding the methylated samples, Me-SBA-16 shows better behavior than its siliceous analogous. However, this improvement is more likely due to the larger dimensions of the Me-SBA-16 (as were revealed by the three-dimensional reconstruction) than to the functional groups. This highlights again the crucial importance of the textural properties and especially of the cage and window sizes.

The sample Me-FDU-12 shows surprising results. It undergoes a very quick enzyme adsorption (a few minutes) up to almost 40 mg/g, far over the rest of cage-like samples. This phenomenon can be tentatively explained, given the disordered nature of the mesophase. In this case, TEM images showed a random distribution of large cavities forming what is called “mesofoam” in the literature.

3.2.2.1. Leaching of enzyme from cage-like OMM. Fig. 12 shows the results of lipase leaching, in the same way as for channel-like samples. As desired, the presence of small openings hindering the enzyme diffusion has now a positive influence, making the leaching much less marked (expressed in percentage of the initial lipase leached).

Interestingly, the data of percent of the enzyme released are lower in the cage-like materials than in the channel-like ones (compare y -axis scale of Figs. 10 and 12). Besides, all these materials present a saturation curve, similar to that of the KIT-6, Me-KIT-6 and Me-SBA-15 in which either a small diameter, the presence of methyl groups or the tortuosity hindered the enzyme diffusion.

FDU-12 and Me-FDU-12 show the highest leaching. As commented in the above paragraph, window sizes of FDU-12 are very likely larger than those of SBA-16, and also probably larger than enzyme dimensions. Therefore, fewer restrictions to enzyme release can be expected. The amorphous foam-like nature in the methylated sample suggests the idea that the enzyme could be entrapped only in the superficial cages (connectivity with the internal core is not guaranteed). The different structure of both materials makes difficult the comprehension of the phenomenon in this case. It is noteworthy mentioning that the methylated sample is more resistant to leaching but again it is difficult to assert if this can be due to the higher hydrophobicity.

SBA-16 sample underwent an initial leaching of enzyme only of 2% that did not increase during the 2 h incubation, which might be attributed to the enzyme molecules located on the external surfaces of the particle. Since no more enzyme was released, it could be assumed that enzyme within cages was permanently retained. Its methylated analogue Me-SBA-16 displayed a higher leaching value, in contrast to the behavior of the channel-like Me-KIT-6 and Me-SBA-15 samples described above. However, there is an additional factor this time: unlike the results obtained so far, the windows size is wider in the methylated mate-

Fig. 12. Leaching of enzyme from cage-like materials. Expressed as percent of the initial enzyme leached on each material as a function of time.

Fig. 13. Activity of cage-like derivatives. Expressed in units of tributyrin converted per milligram of enzyme inside the solid.

rial. This is probably the reason for the higher release of the enzyme, rather than the low hydrophobicity of the walls.

Saturation shape patterns and lower percent of enzyme released clearly indicate that these systems (especially SBA-16) are very resistant to enzyme losses. This finding is of utmost relevance for immobilized enzyme applications, since release of protein from the catalyst is not acceptable in most industries. This might make unnecessary the use of covalent bonding, with the corresponding disadvantages regarding the number of steps, use of toxic compounds in the obtention of the catalysts and often also activity losses.

3.2.2.2. Hydrolytic activity of the cage-like supports. Fig. 13 shows the results of catalytic activity towards the hydrolysis of tributyrin for the cage-like derivatives.

In the samples with *Im-3m* symmetry SBA-16, the tendency is similar to that observed for channel-like materials, that is, the methylated Me-SBA-16 shows higher activity than its purely siliceous parent material. The reasons are probably the same: decreased enzymatic aggregation, local increase in substrate concentration and enhanced diffusion of substrates and products. However, the activity improvement is less marked this time, probably because the incomplete incorporation of the organic function makes the hydrophobicity to be even lower than in the other cases.

One more time, the Me-FDU-12 has a different behavior than the other samples, with a significantly increased activity. As described in the experimental section, the synthesis of this material was performed with a higher degree of methylation, so the microenvironment of the immobilized enzyme should be more hydrophobic than in the other samples. Therefore, apart from the effects described above, in this case the increase in tributyrin local concentration in the surroundings of the enzyme may be even higher than in the other samples, and consequently the rate of reaction would be also higher.

4. Conclusions

The ability to synthesize the OMM with different and known structural and textural properties (including surface hydrophobicity) has made possible to clarify the effect of some of their main parameters on the immobilization of lipase.

In relation with the textural properties, the pore size is the most important factor. Restrictions to internal diffusion in channel-like siliceous OMM disappear when the diameter is twice the one of the enzyme. Larger pores do not yield better results, neither higher enzymatic loading nor lower contact time. Other textural properties such as the total pore volume or surface area are not limiting, as they are very high compared with the enzyme loading. Structural properties such as the bigger tortuosity or connectivity of the porous network do not induce important changes either.

The surface hydrophobicity is also an issue, as catalytic activity of methylated materials is higher than that for the pure-silica ones, both in channel and cage-like materials. Furthermore, the presence of methyl groups and the different degrees of connectivity do have a marked positive influence in preventing the leaching of enzyme when supports are suspended in aqueous media, probably due to a certain stabilization of the lipase when it is occluded inside the channels.

The crucial role of the shape of the pores regarding the diffusion of an enzyme inwards and outwards the support particle has been stated. One-dimension channel-like pores have shown to promote the least diffusional restriction to enzyme immobilization but the highest leaching, similar to that of wide pore amorphous materials. Three-dimensional channel-like pores are the middle case, and the cage-like pores provided the highest diffusional restrictions but the least leaching. In the extreme situation, the lipase was fully retained in cage-like material SBA-16. This new system prevents enzyme release from the support avoiding the need to use covalent bonding to the preexisting support. These results would not be possibly achieved using amorphous materials, and reveal the relevance of the control of the internal structure of the supports for enzyme immobilization. These encouraging findings open novel and interesting prospects for ordered mesoporous materials, and a new scenario in enzyme immobilization.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found, in the online version

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